

LEVELS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPMENT OF OLIGOPHRENIA

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Abstract. This article provides information about the clinical forms and types of oligophrenia. Oligophrenia is a congenital or acquired retardation of mental development up to the age of three, caused by genetic factors or inherited diseases. Intelligence tests are used to assess the degree of retardation. Oligophrenia in children is often accompanied by congenital physical defects.

Key words: oligophrenic, defect, character, injury, age, imbecile, idiotic, defectologist, educator, teacher.

Oligophrenic children differ from other anomalous children in that cognitive function decreases as a result of organic diseases of the central nervous system, and these defects persist for life.

In practice, the terms "mental retardation", "oligophrenic", "dementia" are often used. "Intellectual retardation" is a collective concept, the time of mental retardation, the nature of the disease experienced, the course of pathological changes. , considers issues related to the level.

Clinical, psychological and pedagogical criteria should be distinguished when defining mental retardation. Clinical criterion - mental retardation and what organic diseases of the central nervous system are related to it, psychological criterion- constant disturbance of cognitive activity; Pedagogical criterion is low learning ability, which means that the child cannot learn the program materials.

Oligophrenia is caused by damage and disease of the child's central nervous system during the period of mother's womb, during birth and in the period from birth to 3 years. If, due to various reasons, mental weakness appears after the age

of 3, it is called acquired mental weakness - dementia. Dementia is progressive, that is, it gets worse by nature. In oligophrenia, there is no worsening of the defect.

According to the causes of origin, oligophrenia can be congenital and acquired.

Congenital oligophrenia can be caused by rhesus factoroma, chromosomal disorders, phenylketonuria, etc.

Various diseases of the mother during pregnancy - infection with severe viral flu, typhoid, rubella, transmission of various parasites from the mother's body to the fetus, damage to the fetus, alcoholism of the parents, can also cause oligophrenia.

Oligophrenia can be caused by taking the child with a vacuum or a vacuum extractor during childbirth, compression of the child's head, long passage of the child through the birth canal, protracted or, on the contrary, excessively fast delivery, resulting in damage to the central nervous system. .

Oligophrenia also occurs as a result of a child falling ill with various serious diseases (meningitis, meningoencephalitis, damage to the central nervous system) before the age of three.

According to mental (intellectual) development, oligophrenia is manifested at three levels: 1) stupidity; 2) hypocrisy; 3) idiocy.

Mental retardation is the mildest degree of oligophrenia, and such a child cannot be distinguished from healthy peers based on their appearance. In general, children have a lot of difficulty in tasks related to intelligence and understanding, but if they go to an auxiliary school and master the program, they can engage in ordinary work in the field of industrial and agricultural production. Educators and teachers should separate children from other children and ensure that they are brought up and educated in special kindergartens and schools, or involve them in integrated education.

Imbeciles and idiots cannot afford to be educated even in a remedial school

program. They are idiotic children who are less behind in the development of the Ministry of Social Welfare, unfortunately, they are sometimes found in auxiliary schools. They cannot master the auxiliary school program. Idiot children don't even know their own parents. They cannot do it on their own. He cannot serve himself. Imbecile children are not able to lead an independent life, even though they are relatively more developed than idiot children. In institutions under the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population, they are taught simple knowledge, some simple types of work (self-service, crop care, making cardboard boxes, etc.).

At all three levels of oligophrenia, educators and teachers should be able to distinguish oligophrenic pupils from healthy peers and children with other similar deficiencies. But distinguishing the mildest degree of oligophrenia - debilitation from other similar anomalies and from healthy children is actually quite difficult.

Stupid children differ from their healthy peers from a young age. In them, as a rule, complex movements of a voluntary form are not developed. They learn to hold their head, sit, walk later, and their speech develops late. Stupid children understand the simple speech of the people around them, but they cannot understand complex words and phrases. Even if there are no gross, unintelligible defects in the speech of a mentally retarded child, many sounds are pronounced incorrectly, such a child's vocabulary is poor and limited. Stupid children also differ from their peers in game activities. They do not understand the game situation enough, they completely obey their healthy peers during the game and play secondary roles.

A number of cognitive deficits are characteristic of retarded children. My ability to observe, compare, distinguish the important aspects of what I perceive, events and phenomena, and understand the simplest cause-and-effect connections between them will not develop. A mentally retarded child's thinking, attention, intuition and perceptions, memory, analysis and synthesis skills are not well developed.

Oligophrenic children cannot adequately understand the situation, they cannot even adequately change their actions depending on the situation. They have a somewhat weak critical attitude towards themselves and others. Despite a number of shortcomings indicated above, as a result of properly organized special educational work with oligophrenic children, speech pathologists are making great progress in preparing them for independent life and vocational training. Having received education in special auxiliary labor schools, children have found their place in life and are actively working in various fields of industrial and agricultural production, in the field of domestic service. An important task of educators and teachers is to distinguish oligophrenic children from other anomalous children and is to ensure that they receive education in appropriate institutions as early as possible.

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